

Learning Indicators as Tools for Continuous Improvement in the Educational Environment

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14062523>

Abstract

In today's fast-paced world characterized by rapid knowledge evolution and increasing information valuation, the education sector faces unprecedented challenges. These challenges require a continuous commitment to the evaluation and enhancement of pedagogical practices, adapting them to emerging needs and challenges. In this context, learning indicators emerge as fundamental instruments, offering detailed insights into the efficiency of active learning methods and strategies, and student progress in the development of essential competencies. This article is dedicated to exploring the implementation of two key indicators in the educational environment, aiming at optimizing the quality of teaching and learning in engineering course disciplines. The first indicator analyzed focuses on identifying students' prior knowledge and assimilating new concepts, fundamental for meaningful learning. The second indicator seeks to evaluate the consolidation of engrams, that is, the formation and reinforcement of memories related to learned concepts, allowing the identification of gaps in the teaching-learning process. It is argued that the adoption of these indicators, among others, is necessary for effective educational management, allowing not only the monitoring and evaluation of pedagogical practices but also the planning of precise and well-founded interventions to establish an inclusive, efficient, and motivating learning environment.

Keywords: Learning Indicators; Active Learning; Teacher Training; A3M.

1 Introduction

In today's fast-paced world characterized by rapid knowledge evolution and increasing information valuation, the education sector faces unprecedented challenges. These include the urgent need to integrate digital technologies into educational practices to align with the evolving professional skills required by the workforce and to improve educational outcomes at scale (Diogo et al., 2023; Fomunyam, 2019; Hattie, J., 2009).

Traditional pedagogical practices are being questioned, making it imperative to seek methods that ensure the effectiveness and relevance of education. Learning indicators, analytical tools designed to measure and evaluate specific aspects of the educational process, emerge as key elements in this scenario (Prince, 2004; Christie & Graaf, 2017; Hartikainen et al., 2019).

In this context, the Learning for the Third Millennium Program – A3M (2017) is tasked with collaborating with the University of Brasília community to identify, value, and promote innovative educational actions, aiming to provide a sustainable portfolio of methodologies, processes, and applications for use in the university's programs.

As a way to promote more effective teaching and learning strategies within the scope of the program, the calls for proposals to encourage innovative educational projects for undergraduate teaching now require the use of learning indicators to demonstrate evidence of learning gains in the final reports of the awarded projects.

This article focuses on the implementation and analysis of two specific indicators related to learning from the point of view of neuroscience, proposed by the committee that coordinates the A3M program (Ramos et al., 2023). The two indicators were implemented in two engineering program courses, involving three classes each one, in educational environments that employed variations of active learning methods and strategies. In these courses, the practical application of knowledge and the development of technical skills are prioritized, without leaving aside the soft skills, and highlighting the importance of aligning educational theory with practical demands. These approaches emphasize the need to integrate theoretical knowledge with concrete practical experiences, aiming for a more comprehensive education tailored to the demands of the professional market.

A literature review reveals difficulties regarding the systematic application of learning indicators and their impact on the continuous improvement of pedagogical practices (Prince, 2004; Christie & Graaf, 2017; Hartikainen et al., 2019). Therefore, this study aims to deepen the understanding of how specific "classroom indicators" can optimize the quality of teaching and learning, from identifying students' prior knowledge to evaluating their motivation and engagement.

By critically analyzing the potential of indicators as continuous improvement tools, this article highlights their importance for effective educational management and the establishment of an inclusive, efficient, and motivating learning environment. The goal is to illuminate the path for more informed and evidence-based pedagogical interventions, offering significant contributions to the academic community and education professionals. This approach promotes a culture of continuous evaluation and improvement in teaching practices.

2 Active Learning Outcomes

According to Christie & Graaf (2017, p. 11), "Constructivism, which has helped shift the emphasis in formal educational systems from a focus on the teacher to various forms of student-centred learning, has provided a basis for a number of pedagogical models." These models, in turn, can encompass instructional methods and strategies of active learning.

By placing the student at the center of the educational process and encouraging active rather than passive participation, the approaches derived from these models spark interest in improving engineering education. The effectiveness of these approaches in preparing engineering students for real professional demands has been recognized in various studies, as they facilitate the understanding and application of technical concepts and foster essential skills in problem-solving and collaboration (Prince, 2004; Christie & Graaf, 2017; Hartikainen et al., 2019).

Defining strategies to measure student progress and provide necessary feedback for formative adjustments is an important step to ensure that desired educational outcomes are achieved. An aspect highlighted by Prince (2004) involves the challenges that engineering faculty face in assessing the efficacy of active learning. Relying on empirical studies published in scientific articles, it is often difficult to understand what is being studied and how improvements are measured and interpreted, as many methods are grouped under the term "active learning". Evaluating what works may involve analyzing a broad range of learning outcomes and quantifying the reported improvements. According to the author, educational studies, although useful, have limitations and do not guarantee that the same methods will produce similar results in different contexts.

Regarding indicators used to measure the impact of active learning on student learning outcomes, Hartikainen et al. (2019) conducted a review of empirical articles, identifying associated learning outcomes and how they are measured. They found that most are based on self-reported data from students, focused on the

development of course-specific knowledge, and highlight the need for studies to enhance the transparency of empirical interventions and the application of active learning.

In this context, it is clarified that the intent of this work is not to evaluate the efficacy of the active learning methods and strategies used, but rather, to characterize the learning environment utilized in the application of the presented indicators.

The strategies used in the applications are the Flipped Classroom and Peer Instruction, and the methods are Problem-based Learning and Team-based Learning. Detailed explanations can be found in Elmôr-Filho et al. (2019), Villas-Boas & Sauer (2019), and Burgess, McGregor & Mellis (2014).

3 Learning Indicators Based on Neuroscientific Concepts

To effectively utilize indicators based on neuroscientific concepts, it is essential to deepen our understanding in this field. This broader knowledge will support the comprehension of both the indicators themselves and their contributions to teaching. In this context, this text presents key aspects that can aid and enhance knowledge about neuroscience, specifically related to the indicators developed by the authors, based on the work of Ramos et al. (2023).

From a neurobiological perspective, learning is a cerebral process that involves acquiring new skills, marking an initial phase in the broader memory process, which includes acquisition, retention, consolidation, and recall of information. According to Izquierdo (2002), the memory process consists of these stages, where the processing of sensory, experiential, or linguistic experiences stimulates the reconstruction of neural assemblies in a constant flow of information. These abilities, whether cognitive or motor, are retained and recalled as needed.

Therefore, learning, known as the construction of knowledge, results in the integration of new information into pre-existing knowledge and requires the proper functioning of brain structures as well as an appropriate conscious state. Changes are constantly required as we are perpetually assimilating new information and electrical stimuli that travel through neurons and can be cataloged and stored in various brain regions, known as memory engrams. This remarkable ability to add new knowledge to previously consolidated information in memory, forming networks and reprocessing what has been learned, characterizes neuroplasticity.

In this context, indicator 1 was developed.

Memory consolidation is the key process that allows acquired information to be stored in neural circuits for long periods, enabling recall and adaptation over time. This process, essential for the formation of long-term memory, relies on neuroplasticity—a feature of the brain that allows it to mold and react to new information through the repetition of data and associated emotional stimuli. By leveraging neuroplasticity in educational settings, we aim to solidify this information within our students' brains, ensuring that it remains accessible and applicable as needed.

Cognitive neuroscience identifies this reinforcement of memory as the elaboration of an established mental lexicon, enriching it as new information is integrated. This involves not only learning specific terms but also their attributes and uses, which are then woven into the existing cognitive network. As new related concepts are added, this network becomes increasingly complex, enhancing students' ability to innovate and apply their knowledge successfully to future projects and professional tasks. This enriched network not only supports

academic and professional success but also fosters the capability to generate novel solutions to emerging challenges.

From these concepts, Indicator 2 was developed.

Below are presented the two classroom performance indicators based on concepts from neuroscience discussed.

3.1 New Concept Acquisition Indicator

In this indicator, both the prior knowledge of students and the acquisition of new concepts can be identified. It is important to first assess prior knowledge to identify concepts previously acquired but necessary for the synaptic enrichment and strengthening induced by the course.

A form should be administered at the beginning and end of the semester, or before and after the completion of a module of new knowledge to be acquired.

The instructor creates a comprehensive list of prior concepts and those to be acquired throughout the course or module. The richer and more detailed the list, the more complete the instructor's understanding of the students' prior knowledge will be.

After generating the list of prior and new concepts, the instructor will present the list with knowledge markers, as indicated below:

1. I have never heard of this concept.
2. I have little knowledge.
3. I have partial knowledge about the subject.
4. I have full knowledge.
5. I have full knowledge and know how to apply it.

When assessed at the beginning of the semester, the indicator provides a list of concepts that are more widely mastered by students, while at the end of the module or semester it will indicate the percentage increase in concepts learned. This difference also helps to identify concepts that are poorly incorporated by students, as well as concepts that were greatly reinforced during classes.

3.2 Connection Network Enrichment Indicator

This indicator is useful for identifying the formation and enrichment of engrams, a result of neuroplastic changes, which make long-term memory more complex and recall capabilities more effective. The formation of engrams results from these neuroplastic changes. The indicator also helps in assessing which concepts have been consolidated and which still require reinforcement. It can be introduced to students at the beginning or end of the semester or module, or only at the end of the period.

The teacher presents a single key term and asks the students to list the entire network of information associated with the term. The increase in the network of connections formed over the semester or during the teaching activity is calculated. The quality of elaboration and the effectiveness of integrating correct concepts into the topic in question result in an increase in the connections made by the student. As the elaboration becomes richer and the correct concepts are more effectively linked to the topic addressed, the greater the number of connections made by the students. One approach to analyzing these results is to calculate the average percentage of concepts that students can recall individually and as a group. Further analyses can be conducted on concepts that were not mentioned or were only rarely cited, providing insight into the concepts that were not integrated into the memory engrams.

Considering that the context of applying indicators based on neuroscientific knowledge involves active learning methods and strategies, the following section introduces these approaches.

4 Application Scenarios

Two application scenarios are presented, each involving one of the previously introduced indicators. The first scenario relates to a module from the Machine Design course in the Mechanical Engineering program at the University of Brasília, Darcy Ribeiro Campus. This module was implemented in three different ways, on three separate occasions, each lasting three weeks with four hours of weekly classes, involving three classes and a total of 48 students.

The second scenario pertains to the Software Quality course in the Software Engineering program at the same university, but at the Gama Campus. This course was conducted twice, in different academic semesters, each lasting 15 weeks with four hours of weekly classes. It involved three classes each time, and a total of 93 students.

4.1 New Concept Acquisition Indicator

This indicator was used to help assess the impact of different teaching approaches and to understand whether methodological changes resulted in significant improvements in understanding and knowledge retention.

The indicator was applied in the first module of the Machine Design course, which is one of six modules, on three occasions: 2021.2, 2023.2, and 2024.1, in classes of, respectively, 14, 17, and 17 students. In 2021.2, the PBL (Problem-Based Learning) method was used; in 2023.2, the strategies of Flipped Classroom and Peer Instruction were employed; in 2024.1, both the Flipped Classroom strategy and the PBL method were used. PBL followed the approach proposed by Ribeiro (2015). The Flipped Classroom involved watching a video lecture lasting between 10 and 20 minutes before each class session and answering a digital questionnaire with 5 questions about the topic, before classroom activities. The Peer Instruction strategy was implemented as described in ELMÔR-FILHO et al. (2019).

4.2 Connection Network Enrichment

This indicator was implemented in the Software Quality course, part of the Software Engineering undergraduate program at the Gama Faculty, University of Brasília, over two academic semesters: the first semester of 2023.1 (with one class) and the second semester of 2023.2 (with two classes). The indicator was collected in all three classes at both the beginning (first round) and the end of the semester (second round). In the 2023.1 semester, conventional teaching methods were used with lecture-based classes and a final course project, while in the following semester, Team Based Learning (TBL) was implemented.

Using the key term "Software Quality," students were invited to list related terms that came to mind spontaneously. Subsequently, given the large number and diversity of terms mentioned by the students, categorization was carried out into four main thematic groupings: C1: Software quality characteristics; C2: Software quality assessment; C3: Software process quality; and C4: Software product quality.

Interpretations derived from this indicator can be conducted considering two perspectives: that of the discipline itself and that of the student body. When viewed through the lens of the discipline, the indicator reveals topics that require more attention and deeper exploration. On the other hand, when focusing on the students, it becomes feasible to identify which groups or specific individuals could benefit from activities exploring a yet unfamiliar theme.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 New Concept Acquisition Indicator

To assess learning outcomes in the first module of the Machine Design course, a digital form with a list of 34 concepts—both pre-existing and acquired during the module—were utilized. Students rated their knowledge of each concept using a 5-point Likert scale to indicate the option that best represented their understanding. Only students who completed the assessment at both the beginning (Round 1) and end of the module (Round 2) were included in the analysis. As a result, the responses of 9, 13, and 10 students were counted for the academic periods of 2021.2, 2023.2, and 2024.1, respectively.

To facilitate comparisons between the strategies used, averages were calculated for all concepts in Rounds 1 and 2 for all students who completed the forms during both rounds. Bar graphs were constructed to visualize the scores for each case (Figure 1). These graphs show an expected improvement from Round 1 to Round 2. Specifically, in 2021.2 using the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) method, there was an increase of 66.5%; in 2023.2 with the Flipped Classroom and Peer Instruction approach, the increase was 63.7%; and in 2024.1 combining Flipped Classroom and PBL, the increase reached 75.2%. Notably, the combined strategy of Flipped Classroom and PBL in 2024.1 yielded the highest percentage increase. Given the limited number of students involved in these analyses, drawing conclusions about the most effective combination of strategies requires further study.

Figure 1. Comparison of educational strategies adopted in Machine Design course by year and phase

Figures 2 and 3 display the five concepts with the smallest and largest differences between the two phases for the Flipped Classroom + Peer Instruction and Flipped Classroom + PBL strategies. The results indicate that concepts with smaller differences generally represent prior knowledge, while those with larger differences are newly introduced concepts. A mean score of 4.0, achieved in several concepts, signifies full comprehension. However, the desired outcome is for students to be able to apply this knowledge effectively.

Figure 2. Concepts with top 5 (a) smallest and (b) largest differences for Flipped Classroom + Peer Instruction strategies

Figure 3. Concepts with top 5 (a) smallest and (b) largest differences for Flipped Classroom + PBL method

This indicator provides individual average scores for the set of concepts. Table 1 shows the percentage increase of scores from Phase 1 to Phase 2 for each student. It is noted again that an average score of 4.0 indicates that the student has a full understanding of the concept set. Shaded cells highlight that students B, C, F, G, and H require additional attention.

Table 1. Percentage increase of scores from Round 1 to Round 2 for each student in 2024.1.

Student	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
Average of scores Round 1	1.78	2.61	3.00	1.69	2.36	2.17	2.19	2.08	2.14	1.67
Average of scores Round 2	4.33	3.72	3.36	4.00	4.67	3.61	2.00	3.36	4.58	4.36
Increase	144%	43%	12%	136%	98%	67%	-9%	61%	114%	162%

It is possible to identify the concepts that received the lowest average scores, which also require attention: Deflection from Castigliano's Theorem (2.79), Bergstrasser Factor (3.14), Musical Wire (3.29), Robust Linearity (3.29), and Wahl Factor (3.29). These were the concepts least effectively assimilated by the students.

5.2 Connection Network Enrichment Indicator

As previously mentioned, a total of 93 students participated in the study of this indicator. In 2023.1, 33 students participated, representing 67.3% of a class of 49 students. In 2023.2, Class 1 had 23 students, corresponding to 63.9% of a total of 36 students. Class 2 consisted of 37 students, representing 78.0% of a class of 47 students.

Upon analyzing this indicator, there is a significant increase in the number of students who evoked terms in each of the categories, indicating a general trend of improvement in term recall from the first to the second round, reflecting an enrichment in the students' network of connections and an increase in information retention over the semester (Figure 4). However, terms from the category "C3: Software process quality" showed the least progress, suggesting the need for more emphasis or a different teaching strategy when addressing this topic.

Figure 4. Connection Network Enrichment Indicator in 2023.1

In the following semester (2023.2), the Team Based Learning (TBL) method was adopted as the teaching strategy. TBL is student-centered and designed for large classes. Under the guidance of the teacher, TBL fosters interaction and collaboration in small groups (Burgess, McGregor & Mellis, 2014). The initial experiences of using TBL in the Software Engineering course at the University of Brasília began in 2017, demonstrating the feasibility of applying the method to disciplines in this area. Both students and teachers provided favorable reports on the continued use of the method (Ramos et al, 2018).

TBL follows a structured approach in three phases. It begins with the Pre-Class Preparation, where the instructor provides bibliographic material at least 15 days in advance, allowing students to prepare for the classroom activities. The second phase, Assurance of Preparation, involves taking readiness assurance tests (RAT) - first individually (iRAT - individual readiness assurance test) and then as a team (tRAT - team readiness assurance test), where students discuss and reach consensus on the correct answers. During the tRAT, the instructor provides immediate feedback. Students have the opportunity to write Appeals, challenging the instructor's answer key based on the material studied in the Pre-Class Preparation phase, fostering a deeper understanding of the theory. Finally, a mini lecture is given to clarify any doubts the students might have. In the final phase, Application of Concepts, students apply the knowledge acquired to solve problems relevant to professional practice.

Similarly to the first semester of 2023, the results from the second semester of 2023 (Figure 5) show a pattern of improvement in the recall of terms from the beginning of the semester (1st round) to the end of the semester (2nd round), particularly in the category "C2: Software quality assessment" and also in the category "C3: Software quality process". However, the categories "C1: Software quality characteristics" and "C4: Software product quality" showed no variation in Class 1, while Class 2 exhibited more significant changes.

Although more data is needed to establish a more robust measurement base, the current results suggest that the implementation of TBL may have facilitated an increase in the retention or understanding of concepts related to "C3: Software quality process," especially when comparing the classes of 2023.1 and 2023.2. The progress in categories C1 and C4, on the other hand, was more modest. This highlights the importance and usefulness of the learning indicator in identifying the topics that require greater emphasis, regardless of the teaching method adopted.

Figure 5. Connection Network Enrichment Indicator in 2023.2 (a) Class 1 and (b) Class 2

6 Conclusion

This study has underscored the significance of implementing learning indicators in engineering education as important tools for assessing and enhancing educational practices. Through the systematic use of indicators—specifically the New Concept Acquisition Indicator and the Connection Network Enrichment Indicator—we have demonstrated their potential in providing a detailed analysis of both student learning progress and the efficacy of instructional strategies.

The findings reveal that learning indicators facilitate a more nuanced understanding of student engagement and knowledge acquisition, enabling educators to tailor their approaches to better meet educational goals. For instance, the New Concept Acquisition Indicator highlighted areas where prior knowledge was effectively integrated with new information, leading to significant improvement in understanding complex engineering concepts. Meanwhile, the Connection Network Enrichment Indicator offered insights into the students' ability to connect new concepts with existing knowledge.

Moreover, the application of these indicators in different teaching contexts—from traditional classroom settings to innovative active learning environments like Peer Instruction, Problem-Based Learning and Team-Based Learning—has shown that they are versatile tools capable of adapting to various educational methods and contributing to a more dynamic and responsive learning atmosphere.

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